

Positron Annihilation Lifetime Spectroscopy of Dodecaborate Cage Molecules in Aqueous Nitrate Solutions

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Abstract—A fast-fast PALS spectrometer incorporating two BaF₂ scintillation detectors was characterized. The PALS spectrometer was employed to measure a model explosives system having nitrate oxidizing sites and B₁₂H₁₂⁻² reducing sites. Positron annihilation lifetimes and intensities were measured for nitrogen-purged aqueous solutions containing various concentrations of potassium dodecahydrododecaborate K₂B₁₂H₁₂ and potassium nitrate with added carrier-free ²²NaCl. Data analysis was accomplished using the PALSfit software program. The influence of electron scavenging and competition by nitrate ions was measured for various concentrations of potassium nitrate. Suppression of positronium formation by nitrate ions at 5 M concentration was greater for o-Ps than for p-Ps in 0.42 M dodecahydrododecaborate solution. At concentrations above 10⁻² M dodecahydrododecaborate only solutions the B₁₂H₁₂⁻² anion suppressed p-Ps formation.

I. INTRODUCTION

POSITRON Annihilation Lifetime Spectroscopy (PALS) is a nondestructive method of measuring defects in materials by relating the lifetime of the positron (e^+) to defect sizes and electron density within a material sample. PALS is an increasingly popular technique which relies on the observation of electron-positron annihilation (e^-e^+) to infer information about electron density at the sites of positron annihilation.

In a vacuum, the positron, the anti-particle of the electron, is

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a stable particle. However, when it encounters an electron, the e^-e^+ pair can annihilate, typically emitting two photons with energy 511 keV, collinearly in the center-of-mass frame of reference, as shown in Fig 1 [1]. The lifetime of a positron is the time difference between emission, birth of a positron, to the time of its annihilation.

There is a competing process which can delay annihilation. A nearly thermal positron can combine with an electron to form a quasi-stable neutral bound state, the positronium (Ps) “atom”. Two types of Ps exist—ortho- (o-Ps) and para- (p-Ps) which differ only in the spin orientation of the positron and electron. If the spins are parallel, o-Ps forms, the triplet state ($S = 1$), for anti-parallel spins p-Ps forms, the singlet state ($S = 0$). The reduced mass of Ps is about half that of the hydrogen atom, consequently the binding energy of the ground state of Ps is half that of the hydrogen atom, 6.8 eV. [1]

Fig 1. Positron-electron annihilation in the center-of-mass frame of reference.

The annihilation processes for the two types of Ps differ. The lifetimes of free p-Ps and o-Ps are 0.125 ns and 142 ns respectively. The e^-e^+ pair in free p-Ps annihilate forming an even number of photons, most probably two. The e^-e^+ pair in free o-Ps annihilates forming an odd number of photons, most probably three, if it annihilates without external influences.

However near matter, o-Ps can interact with additional electrons having different spin resulting in a shorter lifetime for e^-e^+ pair annihilation. This is called pick-off annihilation. For pick-off annihilation the lifetime of o-Ps is on the order of several nanoseconds depending on the electron density surrounding o-Ps [2]. The lifetime of a positron in a defect-free crystal medium is characteristic of the average electron density in the material. However, in real crystalline materials there are structural defects such as vacancies or dislocations

having a unique local electronic environment which directly influences positron lifetimes. [3]

The lifetimes of positrons in bulk material are measured and compared to defect-free material to determine the relative size and concentration of the defects. Average positron lifetimes in defects, commonly on the order of hundreds of picoseconds, increase with decreasing local electron densities at defect sites. In larger pore-sized defects o-Ps can form. Measurement of o-Ps lifetime in porous media is a standard technique for determining average pore sizes in liquids and solid matrices. Lifetimes of o-Ps atoms inside pores of dielectric media increase with void volume in a well-established way [4].

The PALS technique has been used to investigate properties of numerous types of materials. The types of materials of interest for this paper are those commonly used to form explosives. Chemical explosives are materials which rapidly produce gas and energy in a chemical reaction. Chemical reactions in most common explosives are redox (reduction-oxidation) reactions of molecules consisting of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and oxygen. Typically, the reductant sites are hydrocarbons and the oxidant sites are nitrates. These molecules, when subjected to activation energy, break down and recombine by redox reactions to form more stable, lower energy molecules, typically CO₂, H₂O and N₂. The energy released by the explosive comes from the energy difference in the molecular bonds between the atoms in the initial high-energy state and final low-energy molecular configurations.

Several properties are used to evaluate explosives, including energy density, detonation velocity, detonation pressure and shock sensitivity. Nano-scale pores in micro-crystalline explosive matrices affect all of these properties. Nano-scale voids create in-homogeneities that allow the formation of hot spots in the explosive. These hot spots form by several mechanisms including: friction between crystals, internal shear within a single crystal and void collapse. Nano-scale voids also increase the detonation velocity by offering a lower impedance path for the detonation wave. Voids can be introduced intentionally to control the sensitivity of explosives. However, for insensitive munitions, voids should be avoided as much as possible [5]. The PALS method is potentially useful to determine the void distribution at different locations in an explosives matrix.

PALS may also be used to study the distribution of oxidant sites as well as the distribution of nano-scale pores in explosives. While pores largely influence lifetime of Ps, the concentration and distribution of nitrates largely influence efficiency of Ps formation, hence the relative annihilation intensities. In this work, we studied a model explosives matrix using nitrate anions to simulate oxidant sites and borane cage molecules to simulate idealized nano-pore structures dissolved in an aqueous solution simulating the explosive matrix. Nitro groups and nitrates are oxidizing sites that can act as free-electron scavengers and possibly Ps oxidants, where both may suppress Ps formation. Hence, Ps formation in explosives can be influenced by the concentration of nitrates and their heterogeneity. In aqueous solution containing nitrates the rate of electron scavenging to suppress Ps formation is well-understood [2]. A portion of this research was concerned with observing o-Ps and p-Ps inhibition by nitrate ion in aqueous solutions. Our PALS study of these

features in homogeneous matrices is groundwork that may lead to improved explosive processing and performance.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Positron decay of ²²Na was used as the positron source and birth indicator. ²²Na decays, 90% of the time, by β⁺ emission to an excited state of neon-22, ²²Ne. The ²²Ne de-excites in 3.7 ps by emitting a 1.27 MeV photon. The 3.7-ps lifetime is short enough that it is a suitable birth-indicator, the start pulse for the positron lifetime measurement. One of the two resultant 511 keV photons generated by e⁻e⁺ annihilation is used as the stop-indicator. ²²Na has a half-life of 2.6 years, long enough to generate a relatively constant β⁺ flux for the duration of most experiments.

A fast-fast PALS system, incorporating analog NIM electronics, was used for this experiment. A diagram of analog system's configuration is shown in Fig 2. The detectors are constructed using scintillator crystal made of barium fluoride, BaF₂, manufactured by Saint-Gobain Crystals and an optically coupled photomultiplier tube to measure scintillations. BaF₂ has a very fast component in its scintillation decay (0.7 ns) and a high atomic number which make it attractive for applications requiring both high efficiency and fast response [6]. The BaF₂ crystal is optically coupled to a Hamamatsu photomultiplier tube that changes the optical signal from the detector into an electronic current pulse via a photocathode coupled to an electron multiplier cascade.

Fig 2. Hardware layout for fast-fast PALS detection system.

The crystal size for the start detector is 2-in in diameter and 3-in thick and the stop detector is 2-in in diameter and 2-in thick. The larger crystal size for the start detector is more efficient for capturing the higher energy 1.27 MeV photons of the start pulse. Bias voltage was set to -2300 V on both detector photomultipliers.

The timing resolution of the system was determined to be 197 ps by directly measuring the FWHM of a ⁶⁰Co timing

spectrum and multiplying by the time-per-channel calibration. ^{60}Co is used to characterize the time resolution of a PALS system because during its decay it emits two photons (1332 and 1173 keV) nearly simultaneously. This produces a coincidence timing peak, or a delta function in a single channel of the time-spectrum. Peak broadening observed is a result of noise and is the inherent timing resolution of the system.

Aqueous solutions of the nitrate and borane samples were mixed in-house. They were made from a borane solution mixed with differing concentrations of potassium nitrate. Initially, the molar fraction of nitrates-to-water was intended to closely mimic the fraction of nitrates in trinitrotoluene (TNT), in order to maximize the applicability of the results of this study to use in explosives. This intention was later relaxed to allow for a study of positron chemistry in aqueous solution as related to inhibition of Ps formation.

Potassium dodecahydroedecaborate salt, referenced here as dodecaborate, was used to prepare a stock solution containing 97.4 g of potassium dodecahydrododecaborate methanolate, $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$, salt per liter, 0.42 M in deionized water. Sample solutions were mixed by adding sodium nitrate in varying concentrations to volumes of stock solution. Once mixed, these solutions were bubbled with nitrogen gas for 15 minutes and transferred into a nitrogen-purged glove box to exclude dissolved oxygen.

In order to minimize the source contributions to the timing spectrum, a glass vial with 15 mL nominal capacity was used as a sample container. The vial top is a rubber septum secured by a crimp-on cap, which prevents absorption of gases. Approximately 12 ml of each sample solution was transferred into the sample vial. The vial was crimp sealed under nitrogen. Several microcuries of carrier-free $^{22}\text{NaCl}$ solution were then added each sample solution by syringe through the septum top.

One important consideration in developing a source is to ensure that there is little overlap of annihilation events in the sample which could lead to false stop signals in the PALS system. For a $6\ \mu\text{Ci}$ source, the average time between decays is 4.6×10^{-6} sec. The lifetime of an positron in the material is three orders of magnitude lower. Therefore, there is only one positron in the sample to be measured at any time.

A ^{22}Na planchet source of known activity ($0.293\ \mu\text{Ci}$) was used as the calibration source. The source count rate was determined using the PALS system (3.94 cps). The solution activity was then calculated using the simple ratio

$$\frac{A_1}{\dot{c}_1} = \frac{A_2}{\dot{c}_2} \quad (1)$$

where A is the activity and \dot{c} is the count rate. As a check of the accuracy, and to guard against non-linearity in the counting system, the calculation was repeated for a higher activity ^{22}Na source, $6.02\ \mu\text{Ci}$, whose activity was independently verified using a HPGe detector system. The results of both calculations were averaged and the final source-solutions with nitrate and dodecaborate are provided in Table 1. A second series of solutions with various dodecaborate ion concentrations and no added nitrate were

mixed following the same procedure outlined above. These samples are also listed in Table 1.

Table 1. NITRATE/DODECABORATE SOURCE SOLUTIONS

ID Number	NaNO_3 Conc (M)	$\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$ Conc (M)	Activity in μCi
T112B	0.0	0.42	5.56 ± 0.04
T112C	5.0	0.42	4.43 ± 0.02
T112D	0.5	0.42	3.63 ± 0.02
T112E	0.1	0.42	1.66 ± 0.01
T112F	0.01	0.42	0.68 ± 0.01
T112G	5.0	0	4.19 ± 0.03
T127A	0	0.08	5
T127B	0	0.04	5
T127C	0	0.008	5
T127D	0	0.004	5
T127E	0	0.0008	5
T127F	0	0.0004	5
T127G	0	0.0	5

Each of the solutions identified above were examined using the PALS system described in Fig 1. Spectrum collection times were determined by recording the number of counts from a three-minute spectrum and calculating the time required to obtain 10^6 counts in the spectrum. Collection times varied between 24 and 48 hours.

The lifetime spectra were analyzed using PALSfit [7]. PALSfit uses a least squares fit process in two modules, Positronfit and Resolutionfit, to extract the various lifetime components and resolution function from the measured lifetime spectra. Consult [8] for a detailed procedure to execute PALSfit analyses.

III. DATA

Fig 3. PALS spectra for dodecaborate/nitrate series. Top left: H_2O , 5 M nitrate and 0 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$. Top right: H_2O , 0 M nitrate and 0.42 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$. Middle left: H_2O , 5.0 M nitrate and 0.42 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$. Middle right: H_2O , 0.5 M nitrate and 0.42 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$. Bottom left: H_2O , 0.1 M nitrate and 0.42 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$. Bottom right: H_2O , 0.01 M nitrate and 0.42 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$.

Lifetime spectra collected for the nitrate-plus-dodecaborate solutions are shown in Fig 3, beginning with water, nitrate and no dodecaborate (T112G), then water, dodecaborate and no nitrate (T112B), and then water, dodecaborate and decreasing nitrate concentrations (T112C-T112F). Spectra collected for the dodecaborate-only solution series are shown in Fig 4, beginning with 0.08 M dodecaborate concentration (T127A), with decreasing dodecaborate concentrations (T127B-T127F), down to 0.0004 M dodecaborate concentration. Finally, to quantify the source-contribution in the PALS spectra, a spectrum was taken for a sample prepared using only deionized water and the $^{22}\text{NaCl}$ solution, shown in Fig 5.

Fig 4. PALS spectra for dodecaborate-only series. Top left: H_2O and 0.08 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$. Top right: H_2O and 0.04 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$. Middle left: H_2O and 0.008 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$. Middle right: H_2O and 0.004 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$. Bottom left: H_2O and 0.0008 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$. Bottom right: H_2O and 0.0004 M $\text{K}_2\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}$.

Fig 5. PALS spectrum for deionized water plus ^{22}Na solution.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Results of PALSfit analyses of spectra to determine lifetimes and associated intensities for dodecaborate-only solutions are shown in Fig 6. Four lifetimes were distinguished at low dodecaborate ion concentrations: p-Ps, o-Ps and two lifetimes we identify with a quasi-free positron associated with transient water species. The short τ_1 (~ 135 ps)

lifetime is identified with p-Ps and the longest τ_3 (~ 1850 ps) lifetime has been identified with o-Ps.

Fig 6. Lifetimes and associated intensities of positronic species as a function of dodecaborate ion concentration resulting from PALSfit.

At low dodecaborate concentrations, two lifetimes intermediate between those of p-Ps and o-Ps are resolved (~ 400 and ~ 560 ps). We attribute these to positrons sampling different transient water environments. The smaller lifetime is characteristic of that observed for the positron associated with deionized water. Small concentrations of dodecaborate salt appear to produce aqueous positronic species having the longer lifetime. The intensities corresponding to these intermediate lifetimes sum to the intensity of the ~ 450 ps lifetime in 3-lifetime PALSfit analyses. The shorter lifetime positronic water species (~ 400 ps) is 2.3 times more probable than longer lifetime positronic species (~ 560 ps). This composite intensity is approximately constant for dodecaborate ion concentrations less than 0.1 M. The longer lifetime is possibly due to water structures induced by the dissolved potassium dodecahydrododecaborate salt. The separate contributions to the intermediate positronic water lifetime, τ_2 , could not be resolved into its two contributions at dodecaborate ion concentrations above 0.004 M because of the appearance of an additional lifetime at approximately 250 ps.

Lifetime τ_1 , 135 ± 0.06 ps, was not significantly influenced by the presence of dodecaborate anion until its concentration rose above 0.003 M. The intensity associated with τ_1 lifetime nearly disappears as the borate ion concentration reaches 0.008 M. For lifetime analysis the intensities of τ_3 , o-Ps, and τ_1 , p-Ps, were not held constant at the 3:1 formation ratio, allowing for the influence of conversion and exchange reactions.

Quenching of o-Ps by pick-off or conversion reactions are commonly observed. While p-Ps suppression reactions are less probable due to the short lifetime of p-Ps relative to o-P. Surprisingly, PALS analysis of dodecaborate solutions demonstrates suppression of p-Ps formation at and above 0.008 M dodecaborate. Previous similar observations have been attributed to high inelastic cross section for conversion for a ground state p-Ps precursor [9]. An alternative explanation is Wigner spin conservation for energy transfer relaxation of the Ps precursor. This effect has not been fully explained.

At 0.008 M dodecaborate concentration, a new lifetime appears, 250 ± 8 ps, which we attribute to the positron

associated with the borate cage. Identification of the 250 ps lifetime with positronic dodecaborate ion is supported by our earlier work in which we measured a positron lifetime in solid potassium dodecaborate salt to be 265 ± 11 ps. This lifetime is more likely due to the positron associating with the borate cage ($e^+ \cdot B_{12}H_{12}^{-2}$) than Ps residing inside the cage consistent with theory and experiment [10]. The o-Ps lifetime ($\tau_3 \approx 1850$ ps) and corresponding intensity does not change from the value measured for deionized water with added dissolved dodecaborate indicating that the dodecaborate anion does not compete with o-Ps formation.

Fig 7. Lifetimes of positronic species as a function of nitrate ion concentration at constant 0.42 M dodecaborate ion concentration resulting from PALSfit analysis.

Fig 8 Lifetime intensities of positronic species from three-lifetime PALSfit analysis as a function of nitrate ion concentration at constant 0.42 M dodecaborate ion concentration.

PALS spectra measured for aqueous 0.42 M dodecahydrododecaborate salt solutions having concentrations of potassium nitrate varying up to 5 M were also analyzed using PALSfit. Lifetimes and associated intensities for three lifetime analysis are shown in Fig 7 and Fig 8 respectively. Small concentrations of nitrate ion (less than 0.01 M) influence the lifetime of τ_1 and τ_2 . τ_1 decreased from 245 ps to 136 ± 10 ps, while τ_2 decreased to 418 ± 10 ps. Recall that the 136 ps lifetime is consistent with p-Ps, the 245 ps is consistent with the positronic dodecaborate ion ($e^+ \cdot B_{12}H_{12}^{-2}$). If we assume the lifetime of the $e^+ \cdot B_{12}H_{12}^{-2}$ species contributes in proportion to its intensity, the lifetime of the $e^+ \cdot B_{12}H_{12}^{-2}$ species is calculated to be 275 ± 10 ps, slightly larger than the nominal measured value of 245 ps [11]. The 418 ps lifetime is

consistent with positron associated with water. Nitrate ion concentrations less than 0.01 M in 0.42 M dodecaborate eliminate formation of the positronic dodecaborate ion ($e^+ \cdot B_{12}H_{12}^{-2}$). This fact is most likely due to the greater affinity of positrons for nitrate ions than for dodecaborate ions in water. Oxidation of Ps by nitrate ions, which would enhance $e^+ \cdot B_{12}H_{12}^{-2}$ formation, is not evident [12]. Electron scavenging is not a likely cause of the $e^+ \cdot B_{12}H_{12}^{-2}$ suppression at these low concentrations of nitrate, as demonstrated by the lack of Ps suppression in Fig 7.

If nitrate ion competition for the positron is the cause of this observation, then positron binding in $e^+ \cdot B_{12}H_{12}^{-2}$ is comparatively weak. Nitrate ion suppression of o-Ps by electron scavenging is similar to results for water without presence of the dodecaborate ion [2]. Increasing the nitrate ion concentration above 10^{-2} M had no significant effect on either τ_1 or τ_2 . τ_3 , at 1840 ± 40 ps, did not change significantly (1860 ± 40 ps) with small addition of nitrate ions. However, the τ_3 lifetime and its intensity decreased as expected at large nitrate ion concentrations. This is consistent with the electron scavenging role of nitrate ions.

o-Ps and p-Ps formation are not suppressed by addition of nitrate ion concentrations below 0.5 M in 0.42 M dodecaborate solutions, similar to results for water. Below 0.5 M nitrate ion concentration, the lifetimes are nearly unchanged. Above 0.5 M nitrate ion concentration, o-Ps is diminished in favor of positronic water. The o-Ps is reduced much more effectively than p-Ps by nitrate ion suppression of electron-induced ortho-para Ps conversion and may be due to nitrate oxidation of o-Ps to yield solvated positrons [11].

V. CONCLUSION

A fast-fast PALS system incorporating two BaF_2 scintillation detectors was characterized, resulting in a FWHM of 197 ps. This system was used to measure positron annihilation lifetimes and intensities for varying solutions of potassium dodecahydrododecaborate (dodecaborate) and carrier-free $^{22}NaCl$. PALS analysis of dodecaborate solutions resulted in a lifetime of 250 ps that is attributed to positronic dodecaborate anions. The intensity of the positronic dodecaborate anion is appeared with suppression of p-Ps at and above 0.008 M dodecaborate concentration. This system was also used to measure positron annihilation lifetimes and intensities for varying nitrate solutions with 0.42 M of dodecaborate and carrier-free $^{22}NaCl$. Low concentrations of nitrate ions (less than 10^{-2} M) suppress formation of positronic dodecaborate. At 5 M nitrate ion concentration Ps formation was inhibited by electron scavenging. The o-Ps undergoes additional conversion reactions that are more effective than for p-Ps due to its extended lifetime.

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